

Editorial

Introduction to the January special issue of *IJLS* on language(ing), multilingualism, diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism

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1. Introduction

It is often not easy to have a volume of a special issue focusing on and interrogating heavily-loaded and fiercely-contested concepts such as *language(ing)*, *multilingualism*, *diversity*, *equity*, *social justice*, and *language activism*, all at the same time. For one thing, it is a herculean task and a near-mission impossible effort to treat these concepts together in a compact space like a special issue without not doing an epistemic and scholarly injustice to them. For another thing, with the decolonial turn (Chaka, 2020, 2021, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2020, 2022; Shohamy, 2022; Stroud & Kerfoot, 2021) and the embracing of Southern epistemologies (Chaka, 2021; Makoni et al. 2023; Sabino, 2018), these concepts have had to be re-envisioned and revisited. This is more so if another nebulous concept, *translanguaging*, is thrown into the mix. Yet, this is exactly what this special issue volume does: stacking these vexed concepts up against one another or alongside one another with a view to exploring and interrogating them. Some of these concepts have been explored and interrogated before. For instance, Sabino (2018) adopts a no-holds-barred, facetious view of languages, languaging, metro-, multi-, pluri-, and translanguaging by turning these concepts on their head, thereby opening a new vista of theorising them. Similarly, when scholars like Chaka (2023), Chaka and Ndlangamandla (2023), Chaka et al. (2022), and Rudwick and Makoni (2021) call for embedding some of the concepts explored by this special issue volume within their relevant Southern perspectives, they often do so as a reminder to other scholars that Southern ontologies, epistemologies, and cosmologies often get marginalised and silenced in theorising these concepts.

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On the whole, this special issue addresses multiple realities from the Global South, which are manifested through diversity, inequity, social injustice, and social activism, among other things. Due to the geopolitics of knowledge and the need to shift the geography of reason from the Global North to the Global South (Gordon, 2020), Southern theorists are responding to the necessity to foreground their epistemological positionality in order to undo oppressive 'knowledges', thereby attaining social justice (Singh, 2021). All the papers show theorisation that is grounded on local struggles and activism from Global peripheries. As Singh (2021) declares, people must be encouraged to theorise their knowledge by metapragmatically and metageographically assuming epistemological positions that are meaningful to themselves and to the communities from which they come. In that way, they will be pursuing equity and social justice. We, therefore, observe a concerted effort from scholars from diverse continental backgrounds in this special issue, boldly tackling the initial questions from the call for papers: what is the relationship between diversity, equity, language activism, and social justice? How do language activism and social activism influence language equity and social justice? There is a wide range of case studies that show that language use in different domains is entangled with political, ideological, material, economic, cultural, educational, and human rights issues.

In view of the points highlighted above, it is not enough to merely foreground marginalised and silenced Southern ontologies, epistemologies and cosmologies; there needs to be an element of criticality in doing so (see Chaka, 2021, 2023). Equally, the concepts explored in this special issue volume need not be treated by simply paying homage to them in a *Siyavuma*¹-like manner as if they are saint-like phenomena; they have to be treated with the criticality they deserve.

2. Contents of the January special issue

In line with the point highlighted in the preceding paragraph, Chaka's paper attempts not to pay a *Siyavuma*-like homage to the concepts it interrogates. The paper explores the nexus between multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism within the South African context. It, first, argues that despite the fact that translanguaging is often framed differentially from multilingualism, the latter, nevertheless, serves as its alter ego, its point of reference, and its nemesis. Second, it contends that both multilingualism and translanguaging, as transformative conduits for realising human rights-centric goals such as diversity, equity, and social justice, and as initiatives intended to challenge and dismantle the hegemony of English or Anglonormativity in South Africa, are inherently constrained and hamstrung. Third, the paper unpacks the myth about multilingualism and translanguaging

in the South African context. Fourth and last, it highlights the conundrum of South Africa's multilingualism.

The next three papers of this special issue volume explore the benefits of translanguaging as a pedagogical approach. For example, Nkhi and Shange's paper reports on a study that explored the impact of translanguaging in enhancing communicative competence of university students in three selected institutions in Lesotho. Employing a case study design and focus group interviews, the study found that most students preferred being taught in both the target language (English) and their mother-tongue (Sesotho) instead of being taught only in the target language. This finding, the paper argues, highlights the importance of adopting pedagogical translanguaging in the classroom so that students from all backgrounds can be included in their own learning process.

For its part, Xu and Fang's paper focuses on implementing translanguaging pedagogy in English language education with a view to promoting educational equity. The paper takes a stand that the ideology of monolingualism is gradually failing to meet the current dynamic landscape of socio-linguistic and socio-cultural diversity, despite its prevalence in traditional English language classroom teaching. With this in mind, it contends that translanguaging creates more spaces for students to use their varied linguistic and multimodal repertoires to express themselves and to enhance learning in actual classroom practices. Exploring students' perceptions and practices of translanguaging at a university located in southeast China as its major aim, the study collected its data through semi-structured interviews and reflective journal entries. It employed qualitative content analysis to investigate the ways in which establishing a translanguaging space might facilitate students' access to linguistic and epistemic equity. The paper ends with suggestions and implications regarding the importance of raising students' awareness of translanguaging as a means to embrace all languages, meaning-making resources, and previous knowledge for equitable English language education.

Motaung's paper reports on a study that explored translanguaging pedagogical practices in an undergraduate tutorial classroom at a South African university. The study had tutors and tutees as its participants, and utilised semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions to collect its data. With translanguaging theory as its theoretical framework, it used thematic analysis to analyse its data. The findings showed that translanguaging pedagogical practices have the potential to, (a) assist tutors and tutees in creating a comfortable space for learning, (b) enhance content understanding and collaborative learning, and (c) decolonise tutorial pedagogies. Tutors indicated that they require specialised tutor training on how to use translanguaging in multilingual tutorials.

The last two papers of this special issue volume frame their discussions within decolonisation as a leitmotif. To this end, Ndlangamandla's paper entitled "The coloniality of English proficiency and EMI: Decolonization, language equity, and epistemic (in)justice" critiques the English as a medium of instruction (EMI) policy and a monolingual English language proficiency (ELP) curriculum applied in a university and suggests strategies for epistemic decolonisation. The paper draws on epistemologies of the South and decolonial perspectives to answer two questions: (a) What are the prospects of decolonising EMI in higher education? (b) How can English language proficiency be decolonised? It argues that ELP is premised on epistemic racism, Anglocentric ideologies and an inequitable policy of EMI, and the continued disregard for multilingualism in higher education. The paper, then, proposes that decolonisation strategies, such as solidarity-based epistemologies are necessary to enhance epistemic justice, reduce inequality and transform the EMI and ELP in South African higher education.

Finally, decolonisation has a cross-disciplinary application. This is attested to by Mapuya's paper that reports on a study that investigated the perceived contribution of decolonisation epistemologies in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education in South Africa's Further Education and Training (FET) sector. Framed within the critical theory of education, the study had eighteen accounting educators as its participants, and employed focus group interviews and a questionnaire as its data collection instruments. It discovered the perceived importance of mother tongue instruction in promoting social justice and language equity in accounting education. However, it questions the feasibility, sustainability, and practicability of mother tongue instruction. In view of this, the paper recommends extensive consultations between custodians of education systems and language experts in collaboration with subject content experts together with well-articulated pilot projects. Most importantly, the paper cautions that in the absence of plausible supporting scientific evidence, mother tongue instruction threatens to reverse the gains of social cohesion and the global village delivered by a common language of instruction across the globe.

Notes

1. An isiZulu phrase, whose loose, literal English translation is, "We agree", *Siyavuma* in this case has been used in the same way as political mantras like 'Viva', which politicians expect their supporters to blindly chant every time they (politicians) spew out political propaganda to them (their supporters). This is a chilling reminder that scholars can ill-afford to be blind supporters and followers of concepts and theories; they need to critique them.

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